

SCHOOL ADMINISTRATORS' LEADERSHIP ATTRIBUTES AND TEACHERS' PERFORMANCE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14929529>

ABSTRACT

The performance and behaviors of the school heads have contributed significantly on how the teachers perform their duties and functions. This study sought to determine the school administrator's leadership attributes and its relationship to teacher's performance. It focused on the Secondary Schools Administrators and teachers of Bais City Division Negros Oriental Philippines. The 178 secondary teachers of Bais City Division were chosen to be the respondents of the study. The attributes of an effective leader are measured in terms of self- management, professionalism and ethics, result focus, teamwork, service orientation, innovation, leading people and people management. This study utilized the descriptive-correlation method and employed weighted mean and Spearman rank correlation coefficient to measure the extent of school administrators attributes employed in providing technical assistance to teachers. Results of the study revealed that the overall performance of the school administrators attributes in terms of self- management, professionalism and ethics, result focus, teamwork, service orientation, innovation, leading people and people management is significantly related to the teachers' IPCRF performance. However, the degree of relationship is categorized as weak. This finding implies that school administrators who display better performance tend to have teachers with higher performance as shown in the IPCRF rating.

Keywords: *Leadership Attributes, School Administrators, Teachers' Performance, IPCRF*

INTRODUCTION

Education is one of the catalysts that bring change to our society. It plays a significant role in the improvement and development of every individual's well-being and values transformation. This clearly explains how education is given paramount importance in our society of humankind.

In any educational system, effective leadership is measured not only on how good a principal is in assisting the teachers but also on how an individual can be of authority that influences in building good character. Concerning this, teachers need to be adequately provided by school administrators for positive results (Kinicki & Williams, 2018). However, handling low teacher commitment, demotivated teachers, and teachers' mindset is opposite to the goal, teachers' inability to work in groups and unqualified teachers can cause significant problems in achieving excellence in performance.

UNESCO (2014) pointed out that giving and receiving feedback and keeping each teacher on track are the keys to effective teaching. The school administrators' leadership attributes can help promote a positive work environment that allows the teachers to express their needs in the classroom, which also contributes to their teaching strategies for the desirable outcome.

Despite the constant upgrade in salaries, up-to-date training, and professional development, poor performance still prevails. The data show that in the Department of Education (2011-2012), the country's average NAT score was 67% for the elementary level and 49% for the secondary level, which are considered low in proficiency level. Education Secretary Leonor Briones said that Filipino students' performance in large-scale assessment – which is the National Achievement Test (NAT) – “gravitates towards the low proficiency levels,” especially in Science, Math and English. NAT is administered for Grade 6, Grade 10, and Grade 12 students.

Researchers have focused on administrators' management and leadership styles but failed to concentrate on significant variables that could also affect leadership, such as administrators' leadership attributes examining thoroughly the qualities and characteristics that can influence teachers' effectiveness and performance.

School administrators have different attributes. Identifying the teachers' strengths and weaknesses would be a reasonable basis in deciding what applicable qualities are effective in a particular group. As a result, the school administrators can give the teachers the appropriate assistance in expanding their abilities that would significantly affect their job performance.

This study was conducted to provide a basis of a leadership framework that the schools in Bais City Division would implement to improve school administrators' leadership skills and management ability continuously. Furthermore, this study would give the Superintendents awareness of the trainings and seminars to be conducted among

school administrators with the sole purpose of meeting the standards of quality leadership of any learning institution.

Research Questions

The main objective of this study was to determine the teachers' level of perception of the school administrators' leadership attributes and how they relate to the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) rating of the teachers.

Specifically, it endeavored to answer the following questions:

1. What is the performance of the school administrators as perceived by the teachers in terms of the following:
 - 1.1 self- management;
 - 1.2 professionalism and ethics;
 - 1.3 result focus;
 - 1.4 teamwork;
 - 1.5 service orientation;
 - 1.6 innovations;
 - 1.7 leading people;
 - 1.8. people management and;
 - 1.9 people development?
2. What is the performance of the school administrators as rated by the division supervisors?
3. What is the performance of the teachers based on the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) rating?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the performance of the school administrators and the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) of the teachers?
5. Is there a significant difference in the Office Performance Commitment and Review Form (OPCRF) perceived by the teachers and rated by the division supervisors in the performance of the school administrators?

METHODOLOGY

Research Respondents

The respondents of the study were the public secondary school teachers within the division of Bais City. Only 178 were taken as respondents as determined using the sampling formula. In identifying the number of sampled teachers in every school, simple random sampling was applied in which a set of random numbers is then generated and the units having those numbers are included in the sample. The researcher randomly selected ten respondents from 18 secondary schools of Bais City Division.

Research Environment

This study was conducted in the different public secondary schools within the division of Bais City. This includes 18 schools in the said division. Out of the eighteen schools, eight (8) of these are located in the city proper while ten (10) of them are situated in far-flung areas.

The researcher submitted a letter addressed to the Superintendent of the Deped Bais City Division and allowed her to float and made coordinate with the School Heads. Distribution of questionnaires strictly adhered to the health protocols prescribed by DOH-IATF. Hence, the researcher ensures the safety and security of all the participants of the survey.

The data were collected through the questionnaire method. Questions were designed to elicit vital information on the teachers' perceptions of the school administrators' leadership attributes. The floating of questionnaires was done electronically and personally. For those teachers who worked from home at the time of the study, the questionnaires were sent electronically. The links of the Google form and Microsoft 365 were sent as private messages to the respondents. For those who were on duty, the questionnaires were personally given to the respondents by following the protocols under the new normal.

Research Design

The descriptive-correlational research design was used in this study. It is descriptive because it describes the teachers' (a) level of perceptions on their school administrators' leadership attributes and (b) Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) rating. It is correlational because the variables mentioned are being statistically correlated.

Research Instrument

The questionnaire of this study was based on the Office Performance Commitment and Review Form (OPCRF) Core Competencies which aims to measure the school principals' attributes as perceived by the teachers.

Prior to the formulation of the questionnaire, the researchers did a thorough review of the topic and made consultations with the experts in the field. Likewise, they also sought the assistance of research experts who are also knowledgeable along this line for refinement and validity.

The questionnaire is composed of two parts. The first part was on the personal data of the teachers and their Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) rating. The second part of the questionnaire contained the survey proper wherein it has 53 items under nine categories. The statements describe specific principal

attributes. Teachers' perceptions of principal leadership attributes are important to understand attributes associated with school effectiveness.

Research Procedures

The researchers asked permission from the City Schools Division Superintendent of Bais City and School Principals to conduct the study. After, the researcher proceeded by administering the questionnaires to the respondents. During the survey, the intent and purpose of the study were explained to the respondents. Furthermore, because of the new normal caused by the pandemic, the researchers also did the electronic gathering of data. The respondents were assured that data were treated with utmost confidentiality.

Deped Bais City Division allowed the researchers to conduct the floating of questionnaires following health protocols to ensure the safety of every respondent from the threat of the COVID-19 pandemic.

The researchers conducted the survey questionnaire with the utmost safety measures of all the respondents. To avoid gathering in one setting, the data were collected electronically and personally. Most teachers during the time of pandemic were working at home; thus the survey questionnaires were answered through the links of the Google form and Microsoft 365 and some were sent as private messages to the respondents. For those who were on duty, the questionnaires were personally given to them following the protocols under the new normal.

Roughly, it took 10 to 15 minutes to complete answering the questionnaire. After all the data had been gathered, the analysis and interpretation of the data followed.

Statistical Analysis

Percent was used to show how a part is related to a whole. It was used in presenting the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) rating of the teachers.

Mean was used in getting the average performance of the teachers.

Spearman rank correlation coefficient was utilized to identify the degree of relationship between teachers' level of perception of their school administrators' leadership attributes and the teachers' Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) rating. This test again was selected since the data are on ordinal scale.

RESULTS

Table 1.1
Performance of the School Administrators as Perceived by the Teachers in Terms of Self-Management (n = 178)

Indicators	$w\bar{x}$	Adjectival Rating
1. Undertakes personal actions and behaviors that are clear and takes personal goals and values congruent to that of the organization.	4.174	Very Satisfactory
2. Sets high quality, challenging, realistic goals for self and others.	4.146	Very Satisfactory
3. Sets personal goals and direction, needs and development.	4.124	Very Satisfactory
4. Undertakes personal actions and behaviors purposive and congruent to that of the organization.	4.113	Very Satisfactory
5. Prioritizes work tasks and schedules (through Gantt chart, checklists, etc.) to achieve goals.	4.034	Very Satisfactory
Composite	4.118	Very Satisfactory

Table 1.1 presents the performance of the school administrators as perceived by the teachers in terms of self-management. The administrators' management skill is very satisfactory as reflected in its weighted mean of 4.118. The result implies that the performance of the school administrators exceeds expectations. This further explains that all goals, objectives and targets are achieved above the established standards.

Table 1.2
Performance of the School Administrators as Perceived by the Teachers in Terms of Professionalism and Ethics (n = 178)

Indicators	$w\bar{x}$	Adjectival Rating
1. Demonstrates the values and behavior enshrined in the Norms of Conduct and Ethical Standards for public officials and employees(RA 6713)	4.416	Very Satisfactory
2. Maintains professional image: being trustworthy, regularity, attendance and punctuality good grooming and communication.	4.365	Very Satisfactory
3. Acts with a sense of urgency and responsibility to meet the organization's needs.	4.225	Very Satisfactory
4. Makes personal sacrifices to meet the organization's needs.	4.219	Very Satisfactory
5. Practices ethical behavior and professional behavior and conduct taking into account the impact of his/her actions and decisions.	4.202	Very Satisfactory

6. Improves systems and help others improve their effectiveness.	4.180	Very Satisfactory
Composite	4.268	Very Satisfactory

Table 1.2 presents the performance of the school administrators as perceived by the teachers in terms of professionalism and ethics. The data reveal that the school administrators' performance in terms of professionalism and ethics as perceived by the teachers is very satisfactory with a weighted mean of 4.268. The result conveys that the performance of the school administrators exceeds expectations. This means that all the goals, objectives and targets were achieved above the established standards.

Table 1.3
Performance of the School Administrators as Perceived by the Teachers in Terms of Result Focus (n = 178)

Indicators	w \bar{x}	Adjectival Rating
1. Achieves results with optimal use of time and resources most of the time.	4.118	Very Satisfactory
2. Expresses a desire to do better and may express frustration at waste or inefficiency. May focus on new or more precise ways of meeting goals set.	4.101	Very Satisfactory
3. Makes specific changes in the system or in own work methods to improve performance. Examples may include doing something better, faster, at a lower cost, more efficiently; or improving quality, customer satisfaction, morale, without setting any specific goal.	4.022	Very Satisfactory Very Satisfactory
4. Delivers error-free outputs most of the time by conforming to standard operating procedures correctly and consistently.	4.006	Very Satisfactory
5. Produces very satisfactory quality of work in terms of usefulness/ acceptability and completeness with no supervision required.	4.006	Very Satisfactory
6. Avoids rework, mistakes and wastage through effective work methods by placing organizational needs before personal needs.	4.000	Very Satisfactory
Composite	4.042	Very Satisfactory

Table 1.3 presents the performance of the school administrators as perceived by the teachers in terms of result focus. This core competency deals with how the administrators achieve optimal results and produce very satisfactory quality of work. The composite weighted mean is 4.042 which means Very Satisfactory. This implies that the performance of the school administrators in terms of results focus exceeds expectations. This implies that the school administrator consistently demonstrates and achieves all the goals, objectives and targets above the established standards.

Table 1.4
Performance of the School Administrators as Perceived by the Teachers in Terms of Teamwork (n = 178)

Indicators	$w\bar{x}$	Adjectival Rating
1. Promotes collaboration.	4.455	Very Satisfactory
2. Works collaboratively with others and across organization to accomplish organizational goals and objectives.	4.309	Very Satisfactory
3. Willingly does his/her share of responsibility.	4.264	Very Satisfactory
4. Drives consensus and team ownership of decisions.	4.202	Very Satisfactory
5. Works constructively to accomplish organizational goals and objectives.	4.197	Very Satisfactory
6. Removes barriers to teamwork and goal accomplish across the organization.	4.174	Very Satisfactory
7. Applies negotiation principles in arriving at win-win agreements.	4.140	Very Satisfactory
Composite	4.249	Very Satisfactory

Table 1.4 presents the performance of the school administrators as perceived by the teachers in terms of teamwork. As explicated from the indicators, this attribute focuses on collaboration, shared responsibility, and work ethics. The composite weighted mean is 4.249 which means Very Satisfactory. This implies that the school administrator consistently demonstrates and achieves all the goals, objectives and targets above the established standards.

Table 1.5
Performance of the School Administrators as Perceived by the Teachers in Terms of Service Orientation (n = 178)

Indicators	$w\bar{x}$	Adjectival Rating
1. Participates in updating office vision, mission, mandates and strategies based on DepEd strategies and directions.	4.258	Very Satisfactory
2. Articulates organizational directions, issues and problems	4.213	Very Satisfactory
3. Develops service improvement programs through simplified procedures that will further enhance service delivery.	4.197	Very Satisfactory
4. Adopts service improvement programs through simplified procedures that will further enhance service delivery.	4.146	Very Satisfactory
5. Explains organizational directions, issues and problems	4.135	Very Satisfactory
6. Initiates activities that promote advocacy for men and women empowerment.	4.101	Very Satisfactory
Composite	4.175	Very Satisfactory

Table 1.5 presents the performance of the school administrators as perceived by the teachers in terms of service orientation. As explained by the indicators, service orientation centers on the articulation of directions, initiates activities to resolve issues, and adopts service improvement programs to enhance service delivery. The composite weighted mean is 4.175 which mean Very Satisfactory. This implies that the school administrator consistently demonstrates and achieves all the goals, objectives and targets above the established standards.

Table 1.6
Performance of the School Administrators as Perceived by the Teachers in Terms of Innovation (n = 178)

Indicators	$w\bar{x}$	Adjectival Rating
1. Promotes a creative climate and inspires co-workers to develop original ideas or solutions.	4.157	Very Satisfactory
2. Continuously focuses on improving personal productivity to create higher value and results.	4.112	Very Satisfactory
3. Examines the root cause of problems and suggest effective solutions.	4.090	Very Satisfactory
4. Foster new ideas, processes, and suggests better ways to do things (cost and/or operational efficiency)	4.084	Very Satisfactory
5. Demonstrates an ability to think “beyond the box”.	4.084	Very Satisfactory
6. Demonstrates resourcefulness and the ability to succeed with minimal resources.	4.067	Very Satisfactory
7. Translates creative thinking into tangible changes and solutions to improve the work unit and organization.	4.045	Very Satisfactory
8. Uses ingenious methods to accomplish responsibilities.	4.039	Very Satisfactory
Composite	4.085	Very Satisfactory

Table 1.6 presents the performance of the school administrators as perceived by the teachers in terms of innovation. Innovation in this context refers to creative thinking, personal productivity, and resourcefulness among others. The data show that the composite weighted mean is 4.085 which means Very Satisfactory. This implies that the performance of the school administrators in terms of innovation exceeds expectations. This indicates that the school administrator consistently demonstrates and achieves all the goals, objectives and targets above the established standards.

Table 1.7
Performance of the School Administrators as Perceived by the Teachers in Terms of Leading People (n = 178)

Indicators	$w\bar{x}$	Adjectival Rating
1. "Sets a good example", is a credible and respected leader, and demonstrates desired behavior.	4.264	Very Satisfactory
2. Uses basic persuasion techniques in a discussion or presentation e.g., staff mobilization, appeals to reason and/or emotions, uses data and examples, visual aids.	4.090	Very Satisfactory
3. Forwards personal, professional and work unit needs and interests in an issue.	4.090	Very Satisfactory
4. Persuades, convinces or influences others, in order to have a specific impact or effect.	4.084	Very Satisfactory
5. Assumes a pivotal role in promoting the development of an inspiring, relevant vision for the organization and influences others to share ownership of DepEd goals, in order to create an effective work environment.	4.079	Very Satisfactory
Composite	4.121	Very Satisfactory

Table 1.7 presents the performance of the school administrators as perceived by the teachers in terms of leading people. In the indicators provided, leading people means setting as a good example, using persuasion techniques, and promoting relevant vision for the organization. The table also shows that the composite weighted mean is 4.121 which means Very Satisfactory. This implies that the performance of the school administrators in terms of leading people exceeds expectations. This indicates that the school administrator consistently demonstrates and achieves all the goals, objectives and targets above the established standards.

Table 1.8
Performance of the School Administrators as Perceived by the Teachers in Terms of People Management (n = 178)

Indicators	$w\bar{x}$	Adjectival Rating
1. Provides feedback and technical assistance such as coaching for performance improvement and action planning.	4.225	Very Satisfactory
2. Sets performance standards and measures progress of employees based on office and department targets.	4.213	Very Satisfactory
3. States performance expectations clearly and checks understanding and commitment.	4.107	Very Satisfactory

4. Makes specific changes in the performance management system or in own work methods to improve performance (e.g., does something better, faster, at lower cost, more efficiently; improves quality, customer satisfaction, morale, revenues).	4.090	Very Satisfactory
5. Performs all the stages of Results-based Performance Management System supported by evidence and required documents/forms.	4.084	Very Satisfactory
Composite	4.144	Very Satisfactory

Table 1.8 presents the performance of the school administrators as perceived by the teachers in terms of people management. In this context, people management refers to setting performance standards, measures, expectations, and feedback. As shown on the table, the composite weighted mean is 4.144 which means Very Satisfactory. This implies that the performance of the school administrators in terms of people management exceeds expectations. This indicates that the school administrator consistently demonstrates and achieves all the goals, objectives and targets above the established standards.

Table 1.9
Performance of the School Administrators as Perceived by the Teachers in Terms of People Development (n = 178)

Indicators	$w\bar{x}$	Adjectival Rating
1. Facilitates workforce effectiveness through coaching and motivating/developing people within a work environment that promotes mutual trust and respect.	4.146	Very Satisfactory
2. Cultivates a learning environment by structuring interactive experiences such as looking for the future opportunities that are in support of achieving individual career goals.	4.145	Very Satisfactory
3. Conceptualizes and implements learning interventions to meet identified training needs.	4.112	Very Satisfactory
4. Improves the skills and effectiveness of individuals through employing a range of development strategies.	4.079	Very Satisfactory
5. Does long-term coaching or training by arranging appropriate and helpful assignments, formal training, or other experiences for the purpose of supporting a person's learning and development.	4.075	Very Satisfactory
Composite	4.111	Very Satisfactory

Table 1.9 presents the performance of the school administrators as perceived by the teachers in terms of people development. This core competency focuses on the facilitation of workforce effectiveness, learning interventions, development strategies among others. The composite weighted mean is 4.111 which means Very Satisfactory.

This implies that the performance of the school administrators in terms of people development exceeds expectations. This indicates that the school administrator consistently demonstrates and achieves all the goals, objectives and targets above the established standards.

Table 1.10
Summary Table of the Performance of the School Administrators as Perceived by the Teachers (n = 178)

Area	w \bar{x}	Adjectival Rating
Self- Management	4.118	Very Satisfactory
Professionalism and Ethics	4.268	Very Satisfactory
Result Focus	4.042	Very Satisfactory
Teamwork	4.249	Very Satisfactory
Service Orientation	4.175	Very Satisfactory
Innovation	4.085	Very Satisfactory
Leading People	4.121	Very Satisfactory
People Management	4.144	Very Satisfactory
People Development	4.111	Very Satisfactory
Overall Performance	4.146	Very Satisfactory

Table 1.10 presents the summary of the performance of the school administrators as perceived by the teachers. All areas have weighted means above 4 which can be translated to a rating of Very Satisfactory. Among the areas, the highest weighted mean goes to professionalism and ethics while the lowest is result focus. The overall performance is 4.146 which still translates to Very Satisfactory indicates that the school administrator consistently demonstrates and achieves the goals, objectives and target above the established standards.

Table 1.11
Performance of the School Administrators as Rated by the Division Supervisors (n = 18)

Rating	Adjectival Rating	Frequency	Percent
4.500 – 5.000	Outstanding	1	5.56
3.500 – 4.499	Very Satisfactory	16	88.88
2.500 – 3.499	Satisfactory	1	5.56
Total		18	100.00
Mean = 4.049 (Very Satisfactory)			
sd = 0.413			

Table 1.11 presents the summary of the performance of the school administrators as rated by the Division supervisors. Out of 18 school administrators, 16 or 88% are rated as very satisfactory. One was assessed as outstanding and the other one was assessed as satisfactory. The data show that almost all of the school administrators in the Division

of Bais City consistently demonstrate and achieve the goals, objectives and target above the established standards.

Table 2
Performance of the Teachers based on IPCRF Ratings (n = 178)

Rating	Adjectival Rating	Frequency	Percent
4.500 – 5.000	Outstanding	19	10.67
3.500 – 4.499	Very Satisfactory	154	86.52
2.500 – 3.499	Satisfactory	5	2.81
Total		178	100.00
Mean = 4.019 (Very Satisfactory)			
sd = 0.325			

Table 2 presents the performance of the teachers based on IPCRF Rating. Out of 178 respondents, 154 or 86.52% of them are Very Satisfactory. Nineteen (19) or 10.67% of them are rated Outstanding and the other five (5) or 2.81% of the respondents are graded as Satisfactory. As indicated in the table, majority of them perform the exceeded expectations. This implies that the teachers consistently demonstrate and achieve the goals, objectives and targets above the established standards.

Table 3
Relationship between the Performance of the School Administrators and the IPCRF Performance of the teachers (n = 178)

Variables	r_s	p-value	Decision	Remark
Self- Management	0.225	0.003	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Professionalism & Ethics	0.129	0.085	Fail to Reject H_{01}	Not Significant
Result Focus	0.212	0.005	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Teamwork	0.274	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Service Orientation	0.187	0.013	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Innovation	0.145	0.054	Fail to Reject H_{01}	Not Significant
Leading People	0.170	0.023	Reject H_{01}	Significant
People Management	0.178	0.017	Reject H_{01}	Significant
People Development	0.184	0.014	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Overall	0.238	0.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant

Table 3 reveals the data in identifying the relationship between the performance of the school administrators and the IPCRF performance of the teachers. As shown, the computed p-values of the following variables are less than the level of significance (0.05): self-management; result focus; teamwork; service orientation; leading people; people management; and people development. This finding will allow rejection of the null hypothesis. This means that there is a significant relationship with the school administrators' attributes and the IPCRF performance of the teachers. The school administrators' overall performance is also significantly related to the teachers' IPCRF performance ($p = 0.001 < \alpha = 0.05$).

Table 4

Analysis Table on the Difference between the Perceptions of the Teachers and Rating of the Division Supervisors in the Performance of the School Administrators (n = 18)

Variables	Median	U-value	p-value	Decision	Remark
Teachers	4.011	130	0.317	Fail to	Not
School Supervisors	4.126			Reject H_0	Significant

Table 4 displays the data in identifying the difference in the perceptions of the teachers and Division Supervisors in the performance of the school administrators. Using the Mann-Whitney U test reveals that the p-value (0.317) is greater than the level of significance (0.05). This finding will not warrant rejection of the null hypothesis. This means that there is no significant difference in the school administrators' performance as viewed by the teachers and the supervisors.

DISCUSSION

Performance of the School Administrators

In terms of management skills, the performance of the school administrators is very satisfactory which implies that the performance of the school administrators exceeds expectations. National College for School Leadership (2001) points out that an effective leader is one that creates an environment with shared vision to come up with clear strategic plan for the school. This was supported in a research entitled "A Study to Examine Teacher Perceptions of Leadership Characteristics That Middle School Principals Should Have to Be an Effective Instructional Leader" by McCann in 2011 which states that a leader provides common school vision for reaching established instructional goals for school improvement and student success. Gurr et al. (2010) explain that the principal's sense of direction is an important factor in giving the school clear goals to achieve.

In terms of professionalism and ethics, the results convey that the performance of the school administrators exceeds expectations. This means that all the goals, objectives and targets were achieved above the established standards. This finding is supported in a research conducted McCann in 2011, which revealed that the school leaders should manifest a great deal of professionalism and ethical behaviors. Furthermore, Balyer (2012) concluded that the principals should influence manners at school and should have at least master's degree in educational management field for it gives them enough knowledge and strategies to handle a school to perform.

In terms of result focus, the performance of the school administrators exceeds expectations. This implies that the school administrator consistently demonstrates and achieves all the goals, objectives and targets above the established standards. Inayah (2010) explains that the leaders must be effective and efficient in undertaking the processes done and should have the ability to manage the guidelines and policies of the department. Furthermore, the principals' decisions and strategies are critically important

to institutional performance as they are accountable for high levels of student achievement (Ceatrix Campus, 2016).

In terms of teamwork, the performance of the school administrators is very satisfactory. National College for Teaching and Leadership (2013) posits that school administrators should aim to develop the quality of workforce through collaboration among its members. Zepeda (2014) asserts that the leader should remain his focus on the positive outcome and goals rather than the barriers and cultivates support of the school through its community partnerships. Identifying the right ways to attain excellent job performance entails that a teacher has the ability to put together significant inputs that contribute to the teaching and learning process (Werang, 2014). Further, the National Institute for Excellence in Teaching (NIET) (2012) suggests that in order for the teachers' performance to be effective, there must be collaboration through instructional coaching done by the school administrators to impact both the teacher and student performance positively. Also, Comighud (2019) affirmed in her study that there is a strong and significant relationship between the extent of school heads' implementation of goal setting, monitoring, and feedbacking practices and teachers' job performance.

In terms of service orientation, the performance of the school administrators is very satisfactory. The idea of developing the teachers' skills can evidently increase their competitiveness in the workforce and if on the manner of failure in performing their roles and responsibilities it implies that the leaders fail to provide programs to increase performance. An excellent performance is reflected by the professional growth provided by the school administrators through creating programs that help teachers to improve in the field (Vosloban, 2012).

National College for Teaching and Leadership (2013) also points out that an effective leadership is recognized through creating an environment with shared vision to come up with clear strategic plan for the school. Rantelangi et al. (2017) argued that it is necessary that a leader has to possess the different attributes to handle the different issues and concerns to be solved in carrying out the department's desire to achieve quality education.

In terms of innovations, the performance of the school administrators is very satisfactory. Anderson and Sun (2015) ascertain that a leader is one that is able to inspire and motivate their teachers to follow appropriate attributes to promote greater results. Also, Elrehail (2012) notes that innovation has become vital to the well-being of a country and to the survival of higher education institutions. The research has identified several individuals and institutional factors affecting innovations in higher education institutions including leadership styles and knowledge sharing.

Furthermore, leadership styles have been recognized as one of the most important aspects affecting innovations. With the presence of these issues, transformational leadership comes from its role in enhancing organizational productivity and innovation. The ability to change organizational culture, encourage product innovation, while enhancing the creativity of employees are the significant roles of a school administrator.

Zepeda (2014) insists that leadership has an attitude that promotes and inspires faculty to reach a high set of standards.

In terms of leading people, the performance of the school administrators is very satisfactory. Clifford et al. (2012) cited that a school principals' different attributes such as knowledge, motivation, beliefs, dispositions and actions can greatly influence the school environment, teacher quality and instructional quality. Also, according to Balyer (2012), in so far as their behaviors are concerned, principals are believed to understand how to upkeep the professional needs of the teachers.

In terms of people management, the performance of the school administrators is very satisfactory. According to the study of Pepito and Acibar (2019), performance management as exercised by the school heads is evidently seen in giving support and providing guidance to teachers through instructional leadership. It helps in managing the human resource through technical assistance to teaching and non-teaching personnel. Anderson and Sun (2015) reiterate that the school leaders should equip themselves with enough skills in assisting the needs of their subordinates to solve issues and concerns. In a study conducted by Blasé et al. (2010), the results found out that school leaders should keep on supporting collaboration, developing coaching relationships, encouraging and supporting redesign of programs.

In terms of people development, the performance of the school administrators is very satisfactory. Grissom (2011) and Fuller et al. (2018) listed some of the behaviors that impact on teachers working abilities. These behaviors help the school administrators carry out the goals effectively. Consistent and transparent communication desires to provide feedbacking and consolidation of ideas from the group. Also, the school administrators have to focus on the implementation of procedures to establish a stable environment where teachers can work together confidently. Lastly, there is an immense need to support and encourage teachers in communicating clear expectations, prioritizing trust and respect and buffering teachers from outside influences.

According to the study of Pepito and Acibar (2019), performance management as exercised by the school heads is evidently seen on giving support and providing guidance to teachers through instructional leadership. This kind of leadership helps in nurturing learners through supportive learning environment.

The study by McCann in 2011 revealed that the middle school teachers perceived the principal to be playing a significant role in providing teachers with a focused approach for quality instruction resulting in improving student achievement. Based on the analysis of the findings, teachers perceive the role of the principal to be important in providing professional development. Principals assist teachers with instructional strategies and practices for quality instruction and for improving student achievement conditions for collaborative school culture. Leaders support teacher participation in developing instructional objectives and strategies for meeting student academic needs. Further, leaders provide common school vision for reaching established instructional goals for school improvement and student success.

Another study by Balyer in 2012 found out that the principals' "transformational leadership behaviors have significant direct and indirect influences on teachers' commitment to change and their performance". This study aimed to determine "the level of transformational leadership behaviors that school principals demonstrate during their administrative practices on daily basis". In so far as their behaviors are concerned, principals are believed to understand how to upkeep the professional needs of the teachers. As implied here, the teachers place their trust on their principals and they have great belief in their efforts to move their schools forward. It can also be concluded from the sentiments of the teachers that "the principals respect the teachers and they do not want to use the power against them. The teachers also assert that the principals are good role models and although they are busy with office and paperwork all day long, they always deal with the teachers' problems. Ultimately, it can be concluded that the principals manifest influence manners at school. Presently, many school principals have at least master's degree in educational management field; hence it gives the leaders enough knowledge and strategies to handle a school to perform.

On the other hand, when it comes to the performance of the school administrators as rated by the division supervisors. Almost all of the school administrators in the Division of Bais City consistently demonstrate and achieve the goals, objectives and target above the established standards. According to the study of Pepito and Acibar (2019), performance management as exercised by the school administrator is evidently seen on giving support and providing guidance to the teachers through instructional leadership.

James-Ward (2013) in his study pointed out those principals appeared to have had a successful coaching experience in part because of the coach's knowledge of curriculum, schools, and districts; the practicality of the experience; and the coach's ability to collaborate and shape the thinking of principals without being authoritative or intrusive. The general effects of a coaching focus on core leadership practices may also play a significant part in principal. Principals experienced success on the job is identified by the student achievement and their advancement to leadership roles.

Anderson (2019) reveals that institutions of higher learning, school districts, local, state and federal policymakers of a deeper understanding of ways to better prepare and provide principals ongoing training and support for the complex challenges confronting them in the 21st century.

Performance of the teachers based on the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) Rating

Majority of the teachers perform the exceeded expectations. This implies that the teachers consistently demonstrate and achieve the goals, objectives and targets above the established standards. Excellent performance in any work organization is one indication of a successful workforce. It suggests that commendable performance is the result of self-efficacy and mastery (Sonnetag et al., 2008). Working in a group indicates the total amount of efforts, skills, abilities and opportunities shared together for the common good (Warraich et al., 2014). Identifying the right ways to attain excellent job

performance entails that a teacher has the ability to put together significant inputs that contribute to the teaching and learning process (Werang, 2014).

The National Institute for Excellence in Teaching (NIET) (2012) suggests that in order for the teachers' performance to be effective, there must be collaboration through instructional coaching done by the school administrators to positively impact both the teacher and student performance. For that reason, school administrators have to be strategic in identifying observable effective characteristics and practices.

Relationship between the Performance of the School Administrators and the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) of the Teachers

There is a significant relationship with the school administrators' attributes and the IPCRF performance of the teachers. The school administrators' overall performance is also significantly related to the teachers' IPCRF performance ($p = 0.001 < \alpha = 0.05$). This finding implies that school administrators who display better performance tend to have teachers also with higher performance as shown in the IPCRF rating. However, the degree of relationship is categorized as weak. Gurr et al. (2010) state that principals who role-modeled effective teaching often improve teacher efficacy.

In a study entitled "Examination of Relationships between Instructional Leadership of School Principals and Self-Efficacy of Teachers and Collective Teacher Efficacy" conducted by Calik et al. (2012), instructional leadership had a "significant direct and positive impact on collective teacher efficacy". Moreover, it could be inferred that "teachers' self-efficacy moderated the relationship between instructional leadership and collective teacher efficacy".

Clifford et al. (2012) cited that a school principals' knowledge, motivation, beliefs, dispositions and actions can greatly influence the school environment, teacher quality and instructional quality. Grissom (2011) and Fuller et al. (2018) listed some of the behaviors that impact teachers' working abilities. First, consistent and transparent communication, allows the principal and teachers to share the school issues and concerns to develop solutions. Second, focus on the implementation of procedures to establish a stable environment. The principal's ability implies the knowledge of the standard procedures to be implemented in the school to sustain and organize the flow of activities. Third, support and encourage the teachers, communicating clear expectations, prioritizing trust and respect, and buffering teachers from outside influences.

Significant Difference in the Office Performance Commitment and Review Form (OPCRF) Perceived by the Teachers and Rated by the Division Supervisors in the Performance of the School Administrators

There is no significant difference in the school administrators' performance as viewed by the teachers and the supervisors. Teachers' perceptions came out as one of the most important determining factors that can suggest in designing any training program for their professional development to make them more effective (Grissom et al., 2018).

On the other hand, the main purposes of educational supervision are determining defects and improper practice through controlling educational staff work and taking measures to prevent them, providing staff with coordination, motivating staff through guidance and professional assistance, increasing job satisfaction levels and contributing to the integration of all educational institutions with the environment. The perception of both the teachers and division supervisors is considered positive because it aims to improve leadership, interpersonal relationships, curricula development, and educational development and encourage employees to improve current performance (Warraich et al., 2010).

Conclusions

Based on the analyses and the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The school administrators' performance as perceived by teachers and rated by the Education Program Division Supervisors in terms of self- management, professionalism and ethics, result focus, teamwork, service orientation, innovation, leading people, people management, and people development is Very Satisfactory.
2. The performance of the school administrators as rated by the Education Program Division Supervisor is Very Satisfactory.
3. The teachers' performance based on Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) Ratings is Very Satisfactory.
4. There is a significant relationship between the school administrators' attributes and the IPCRF performance of the teachers.
5. There is no significant difference in the school administrators' performance as viewed by the teachers and rated by the division supervisors.

Recommendations

The Department of Education Division of Bais City should utilize this study's findings in designing an intervention program to develop and sustain the principal's leadership skills and attributes.

Since the relationship between the attributes of the school administrators and IPCRF performance of the teachers is significant, it is highly recommended for school administrators to continue honing the skills of the teachers by allowing them to participate in various trainings and seminars.

Other researchers could use the findings and analyses of this research to conduct further studies to identify other variables and factors that affect the school administrators' performance as viewed by the teachers and the supervisors.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors carefully evaluated all the necessary ethical considerations throughout the duration of the conduct of the study. Information consents were obtained from the participants allowing the researchers to utilize their papers as bases for textual analyses. The anonymity and confidentiality of the participants were also ensured. No conflict of interest existed in the conduct of the study. Furthermore, plagiarism was strictly and firmly avoided and respect for intellectual property was highly achieved. There was no prejudice in the analysis of the results and that, the findings were used purely for research.

Acknowledgments

The authors are grateful for all the unwavering support and ceaseless encouragement they received throughout the conduct of the study.

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